

A methodology and a software tool for 3D reconstruction of coronary and carotid arteries and atherosclerotic plaques

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Abstract—In this work we present a methodology and a software tool for 3D artery reconstruction from Computed Tomography (CT) images. The methodology can be applied in both coronary and carotid CT DICOM images and produces the 3D model of the corresponding arterial segments, along with the 3D models of the calcified plaques. More specifically, algorithms for CT artery identification, vessel segmentation, object extraction and 3d models creation are implemented. The algorithms are integrated in a tool for accurate and semi-automated reconstruction of coronary and carotid arteries. The methodology developed and the steps to use the software tool are presented in detail in this paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

Computed Tomography Angiography (CTA) [1] is a non-invasive imaging modality able to visualize the coronary and carotid arteries. Based on the Hounsfield Units (HU) scale, the inner and outer wall of the vessels can be estimated and the atherosclerotic plaques can be classified to Calcified Plaque (CP) and Non-Calcified Plaque (NCP) [2]. Previous studies [3, 4] have demonstrated that estimations from CTA, like lumen dimension and plaque composition can be performed. Moreover, an accurate 3D reconstruction of the arteries can provide models that allow blood flow simulation and evaluation of the role of the local hemodynamic forces on plaque progression [5]. Several methods have been presented in the past for plaque composition characterization [6, 7]. The outcome of the proposed approaches was compared with the estimations based on Intravascular Ultrasound (IVUS). In [8], they manually detected CP in both CTA and IVUS and compared. With the same approach they have studied the correlation between plaques detected by IVUS and CTA and compared both their volume and areas [9]. In [10], they attempted to correlate the plaque volumes estimated by a plaque characterization CTA software (QAngio CT 1.1, Medis medical imaging systems) and Virtual Histology (VH)-IVUS. All the above mentioned methods require manual interaction for the extraction of the lumen and outer vessel wall borders and do not provide plaque composition characterization or 3D plaque reconstruction. In this work, we present briefly a previous published method for 3D CT reconstruction [11], along with

the developed software application and the provided functionalities.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. CT 3D reconstruction and plaque characterization module

The main purpose of the CT 3D reconstruction methodology is to produce surface models for inner, outer wall and plaque regions. The main steps of the methodology are depicted in Figure 1 and are described below.

Figure 1: CT Reconstruction methodology.

A.1 Preprocessing

Image preprocessing is initially applied on the DICOM images for identifying the potential vessel regions in the CT images. The preprocessing includes the following procedures:

Contrast Enhancement. Contrast enhancement is applied in the CT DICOM stack [12].

Thresholding. The DICOM images are thresholded to create images with potential vessel regions [13].

Frangi Vesselness filter. The Frangi Vesselness [14] is applied to detect structures in the images that correspond to potential vessels.

Large Object Removal. Large objects are removed from the filtered image since they most probably correspond to organs (e.g. the aorta) and are highly unlikely to correspond to vessels.

A.2 Rough Artery Border Detection

The following steps are performed to provide an initial detection of the artery border and extract its centreline:

User Defined Seeding Point for each artery branch. A user friendly interface allows the user to identify seed points for the main arteries. For the CT coronary, three seed points are requested corresponding to RCA, LAD and CFX, whereas only one seed point is requested for carotid arteries.

Region Growing. A region growing method is applied using 26-connected pixels neighbor connectivity for artery region detection.

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Edge Detection. Edge Detection is applied to find artery borders and the border curves can be extracted.

From the artery border curves, an initial centerline is extracted using the center of gravity of each curve [15]. Then the centerline is smoothed to obtain a smooth first derivative of the centerline curve. It should be noted that the centerline is not required to be very accurate for the reconstruction algorithm.

The initial centreline points are fitted with a B-Spline. The B-Spline is used to provide smooth first derivatives needed for producing a radial image, perpendicular to a specific centreline point (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The centerline (blue) with the derivatives (green) on each point.

A.3 Plaque Parameters Adaptation

Lumen, calcific plaque (CP) and non-calcific plaque (NCP) are modeled as a 3-component Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) [16]. The initial parameters are set by the median value of the Hounsfield Units (HU) intensity of the artery. Manual or automated Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm based adaptation is applied in order to best fit the model to artery's HU histogram. The GMM models are used for HU classification in the inner/outer wall and plaque lesion detection.

The GMM is considered in general as a density estimation model. The probability of a sample \mathbf{x} of the distribution for a GMM with L components is given as:

$$P(x) = \sum_{i=1..L} \pi_i N(x; \mu_i, \sigma_i). \quad (1)$$

The posterior probability of the sample x to belong to a specific component, let k , is given as:

$$P(L = k | x) = \frac{\pi_k N(x; \mu_k, \sigma_k)}{\sum_{i=1..L} \pi_i N(x; \mu_i, \sigma_i)}. \quad (2)$$

In plaque characterization, each component of the GMM models corresponds to one of the following classes: (i) inner wall, (ii) outer wall, (iii) calcified plaque, (iv) non-calcified plaque and (v) background. Each pixel is classified to one of the five classes based on the class/component with the maximum posterior probability.

A.4 Inner and outer wall detection

For each equally distant point of the centerline (2 mm) a radial image is produced perpendicular to the centerline point using the B-spline derivatives extracted on the specific point [17]. This image is called the Radial Intensity Projection (RIP). It was discussed previously that the centerline is not required to be very accurate, i.e. not pass

exactly from the center of gravity of the lumen. A very accurate centerline is very probable to produce surface intersections in segments with highly curvature as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: a) The centerline and the intersection imposed on perpendicular surfaces and b) the smoothed centerline where no intersections occur.

On the other hand, the RIP requires that the point should be in the middle of the lumen. For this reason an iterative radial image correction is applied. The iterative process is described by the following steps:

1. The radial image is produced for the given centerline and the current offset (initially offset is zero).
2. The center of mass of the radial image is calculated and a new offset is estimated
3. The process is repeated until the new offset is small enough.

An example of the above procedure is depicted in Figure 4 for a synthetic image with a binary circle with an initial large offset from the center (Figure 4-a). The initial center of the circle is supposed to be the center of the image. It can be observed that after a few steps the radial image is corrected Figure 4-d.

Figure 4: The radial image correction process on a synthetic image: (a) with large offset from the center, b) first iteration, c) third iteration, and d) last (fifth) iteration.

After the correction step, the final RIP image is used for the object extraction process. An example of the RIP image is given in Figure 5-b.

Figure 5: a) The original DICOM image. In the red circle is the vessel region detected using the initial steps and b) the radial image produced taking the radial image corresponding to the centreline point of the specific vessel region.

From the RIP of each slice we extract the ROI of the artery. The ROI is extracted based on the detection of the zero ($<T$) crosses (Figure 6-a). The areas below the zero cross are removed (Figure 6-b). After defining the ROI, the HU profile of the RIP image is calculated for each radius interval (Figure 6-c). Based on the profile, we classify the ROI using the adapted GMM model Figure 6-d).

Based on ROI classification we define profile regions. The inner wall is set to the first non-lumen point. The outer wall is set to the last non-background point (Fig. 7-a). After smoothing, the curves are transformed back to the Cartesian coordinates (Fig. 7-b).

Figure 6: a) zero crosses of the RIP image, b) the resulting ROI, c) the classified ROI, d) the corresponding thresholded image where the calcified objects are detected.

Figure 7: a) inner and outer wall curves, and b) wall curves transformed back to Cartesian coordinates.

A.5 Plaque Region Detection

Using the original radial image, the area between the inner and outer wall is considered as potential plaque region. The classified ROI of the image is thresholded, keeping only pixels belonging to the specific plaque type. Then, large objects are identified and the boundaries of those objects are

extracted. Smoothing is performed on the extracted boundary curve. Based on the physical size of each pixel (DICOM properties) we can calculate the area of each plaque lesion.

B CT reconstruction software tool

The implemented tool integrates all the above mentioned algorithms and it is able to detect the lumen and the outer wall of artery as well as to detect and produce objects corresponding to plaque lesions.

The CT Plaque Characterization and Reconstruction tool has two display modes: i) the single window and ii) the double window mode. For PCs/Laptops with one screen the application runs in the single window mode, whereas for two screen PC/Laptops the tool runs in double window mode. The double window mode allows the user to view in separate screens the workspace of the tool giving the user the ability for a better overview of all the available information. The window on the primary screen (Figure 8) contains the main menu, the 3D render and other statistics and information, whereas the secondary screen (Figure 9) contains image views of the current study.

The user interface consists of:

The 3D render window. This is the main window where the 3D artery is rendered as well as the volume of the CT study.

Axial Image. The axial image for the CT Study.

Sagittal Image. The sagittal image for the CT Study.

Centerline Image. The centerline image for the selected branch

Slice Image. The slice image for the selected slice of the current branch.

Statistics. For each branch there are several useful statistics displayed as charts or text.

Figure 8: Overview of CT Plaque Characterization and Reconstruction main Window.

When a DICOM is properly loaded then in the Render Menu the Branches menu displays the branches currently available for the study. The user has two main options for rendering:

Render a branch. The tool segments an artery on its basic branches. To render a specific branch from the Render menu expands the Branch option and selects the branch of your choice. A dialog will appear on the Render Window and the branch 3D model will appear with the corresponding volume of the slice images.

Render all. In many cases the position of the branch is not

Figure 9: Overview of CT Plaque Characterization and Reconstruction tool secondary Window.

known *a priori*, therefore the user has to identify the branch in correspondence to other branches and the whole artery. For this reason there is the option to render all the branches at the same time. From the Render menu select Render-all and all available branches will be rendered.

The 3D Render Window is the place where the 3D models are displayed and the user can inspect the geometry of the artery and the plaque lesions detected. The 3D render window has several functionalities.

Mouse. The main functionality of the mouse is the zoom in/out with the middle mouse button and the rotation holding the left mouse button and moving the mouse.

Keyboard. There are keys that when pressed, change the appearance of the 3D models. Those keys are:

W: Show object surfaces as wireframes.

S: Show object surfaces as solids.

Clicking over Objects. Objects in the 3D render window can be selected with right clicking on those objects. Selection is enabled for inner wall and plaque objects

Selecting Inner Wall. Clicking over the inner wall objects the corresponding frame is displayed in the axial image window and the centerline image displays the line corresponding to the slice of the inner wall selected and the slice image is updated.

Selected Plaque Object. When a plaque object is selected then information and statistics for the object are displayed. When either the inner wall or a plaque object is selected, the information and statistics are displayed in the left column of the 3D render window. Those statistics are described in Table 1.

Add/Remove Objects. When focus on specific objects is required, the tool can show or hide specific objects.

In the walls and plaques lists for each object, a check box corresponds to the visibility of the corresponding object. Checking/Unchecking shows or hides the objects from the 3D scene.

Object Opacity. In many cases, it is more convenient for overlay objects on volume or visualizing many occluding items. For inner wall and outer wall objects the tool has the ability to make those objects opaque (Fig. 10).

A very important feature for inspecting the quality of the 3D artery reconstruction is the overlay of the model on the volume created from the frames of the study. By default the volume is expanded on the bounding box of the branch that is currently rendered (plus a margin of ± 20 voxels on each axis).

Table 1. Selected object information (plaque information is only displayed if a plaque object is selected).

Information	Description
Current Branch	The current branch displayed
Current Slice	The current slice selected (clicked).
Branch Length	The length in mm of the branch centerline
Min Frame	The minimum frame index that the branch expands.
Max Frame	The maximum frame index that the branch expands.
Total Plaque Volume	The total plaque volume for all plaque objects detected of the same type (calcified/non-calcified)
Plaque Volume	The volume of the current plaque object selected (clicked)
Plaque Surface Area	The surface area of the current plaque object selected (clicked)
Plaque Length	The length of the plaque (mm)
Radius	The radius of the object extended around the lumen
Plaque Expansion Type	Compensatory/Expansive

Figure 10. Object removal and opacity adjustment.

In the 3D render window there are a few options to modify the volume (show/hide volume, apply ROI, change axes margin). Also, in the 3D window the user can measure the remodeling index of a specific branch. In order to measure the remodeling index, two slices have to be selected by the user. The first one is the maximum stenosis slice and the second one is the reference frame. When a slice is selected in either case, then in the 3D render window a rectangle is displayed perpendicular to the artery on the slice selected. When both slices are selected, the inner wall/ outer wall ratio in % is displayed as well as the remodeling index (Fig. 11). Finally, the 3D tool provides statistical information about the reconstructed geometries but also provides capabilities to correct the centerline by modifying and smoothing the generated branches.

Figure 11. Remodeling index slices.

Moreover, the classification parameters of the GMM can be adjusted appropriately for the specific CT examinations for accurate reconstruction. For this purpose the tool provides a user-friendly interface (Figure 12) to adjust the model parameters for each study in order to achieve more accurate segmentation of the artery. The resulting model is visualized in a graph displaying the distribution of each component over the range of HU values.

Figure 12. Classification Parameter Adjustment.

For each component the parameters that have to be adjusted are:

Mixing coefficient. The proportion of each component in the artery.

Mean. The mean of the Gaussian distribution corresponding to each component.

Standard deviation. The standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution corresponding to each component.

Changing the value of any of the variables, the graph of the GMM model is updated accordingly. In order to visualize the result of the segmentation on the 3D reconstruction, the user has to press Re-Render. The Reset button sets the parameters to default values. The Auto-update button automatically adjusts the parameters using an EM algorithm. When user Saves the model, the current parameters are stored in the corresponding XML file.

III. RESULTS - DISCUSSION

The 3D reconstruction tool and consequently the integrated algorithms are tested in several CT examinations including both coronary and carotid arteries. Fig. 13 and 14 demonstrate the baseline and follow-up annotations of the experts regarding the regions of plaque and the corresponding 3D reconstructions provided using volume rendering. The proposed tool identifies the artery and the plaque in the baseline and follow-up and allows for their direct comparison.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Computed tomography can be used for imaging both coronary and carotid arteries. Given the non-invasive nature of the technique, many researchers have focused on it and developed techniques for identifying several key parameters and measurements from non-invasive CT images. We presented a method for reconstructing the lumen, outer wall, calcific and non-calcific plaques in arteries using CT angiography. The method is based on a 3-component GMM.

Figure 13. a) Patient's expert analysis on baseline. b) 3D reconstruction of LAD artery, c) Expert analysis of patient follow-up, d) 3D reconstruction of follow-up LAD artery. Blue labels correspond to correctly identified lesions. Red label correspond to a lesion not detected since it lies on a bifurcation.

The CT 3D reconstruction and plaque characterization is demonstrated as a useful tool for improving the diagnostic capacity of plaque analysis in real time.

Figure 14. a) Patient's expert analysis on baseline, b) 3D reconstruction of baseline LAD artery, c) 3D reconstruction of baseline RCA, d) Expert analysis of patient's follow-up, e) 3D reconstruction of follow-up LAD and CX artery f) 3D reconstruction of follow-up RCA artery. Blue labels correspond to correctly identified lesions. Red label correspond to a lesion not detected since it lies on bifurcation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Eckert J, Schmidt M, Magedanz A, Voigtlander T, Schermund A. Coronary CT angiography in managing atherosclerosis. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2015;16(2):3740–56. doi: 10.3390/ijms16023740.
- [2] Divakaran S, Cheezum MK, Hulten EA, Bittencourt MS, Silverman MG, Nasir K, et al. Use of cardiac CT and calcium scoring for detecting coronary plaque: implications on prognosis and patient management. *Br J Radiol*. 2015;88(1046):20140594. doi: 10.1259/bjr.20140594.
- [3] Papadopoulou SL, Neeffjes LA, Schaap M, Li HL, Capuano E, van der Giessen AG, et al. Detection and quantification of coronary atherosclerotic plaque by 64-slice multidetector CT: a systematic head-to-head comparison with intravascular ultrasound. *Atheroscler*. 2011;219(1):163–70. doi: 10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2011.07.005
- [4] Gauss S, Achenbach S, Pflederer T, Schuhback A, Daniel WG, Marwan M. Assessment of coronary artery remodelling by dual-source CT: a head-to-head comparison with intravascular ultrasound. *Heart*. 2011;97(12):991–7. doi: 10.1136/hrt.2011.223024.
- [5] Giannoglou GD, Soulis JV, Farmakis TM, Farmakis DM, Louridas GE. Haemodynamic factors and the important role of local low static pressure in coronary wall thickening. *Int J Cardiol*. 2002;86(1):27–40. doi: 10.1016/S0167-5273(02)00188-2.
- [6] Wintermark M, Jawadi SS, Rapp JH, Tihan T, Tong E, Glidden DV, et al. High-resolution CT imaging of carotid artery atherosclerotic plaques. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol*. 2008;29(5):875–82. doi: 10.3174/ajnr.A0950.
- [7] Saremi F, Achenbach S. Coronary plaque characterization using CT. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2015;204(3):W249–W60. doi: 10.2214/AJR.14.13760.
- [8] Leber AW, Becker A, Knez A, von Ziegler F, Sirol M, Nikolaou K, et al. Accuracy of 64-slice computed tomography to classify and quantify plaque volumes in the proximal coronary system: a comparative study using intravascular ultrasound. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2006;47(3):672–7. doi: 10.1016/j.jacc.2005.10.058.
- [9] Voros S, Rinehart S, Qian Z, Vazquez G, Anderson H, Murrieta L et al. Prospective validation of standardized, 3-dimensional, quantitative coronary computed tomographic plaque measurements using radiofrequency backscatter intravascular ultrasound as reference standard in intermediate coronary arterial lesions: results from the ATLANTA (assessment of tissue characteristics, lesion morphology, and hemodynamics by angiography with fractional flow reserve, intravascular ultrasound and virtual histology, and noninvasive computed tomography in atherosclerotic plaques) I study. *JACC Cardiovasc Interv*. 2011; 4(2):198–208. doi:10.1016/j.jcin.2010.10.008.
- [10] de Graaf MA, Broersen A, Kitslaar PH, Roos CJ, Dijkstra J, Lelieveldt BP, et al. Automatic quantification and characterization of coronary atherosclerosis with computed tomography coronary angiography: cross-correlation with intravascular ultrasound virtual histology. *Int J Cardiovasc Imaging*. 2013;29(5):1177–90. doi: 10.1007/s10554-013-0194-x.
- [11] Athanasiou L, Rigas G, Sakellarios AI, Exarchos TP, Siogkas PK, Bourantas CV, et al. Three-dimensional reconstruction of coronary arteries and plaque morphology using CT angiography - comparison and registration with IVUS. *BMC medical imaging*. 2016;16(1):9.
- [12] Gonzalez RC, Woods RE. *Digital Image Processing*. 2nd ed. Upper Saddle River, N.J: Prentice Hall; 2002.
- [13] Otsu N. Threshold selection method from gray-level histograms. *Ieee T Syst Man Cyb*. 1979;9(1):62–6.
- [14] Frangi AF, Niessen WJ, Vincken KL, Viergever MA. Multiscale vessel enhancement filtering. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*: Springer-Verlag; 1998. p. 130-7.
- [15] Kokubun H., Miyazaki O., and Hayashi H., Radial intensity projection for lumen: application to CT angiographic imaging, presented at the Medical Imaging 2006: Physics of Medical Imaging, San Diego, 2006.
- [16] Klass O., Kleinhans S., Walker M. J., Olszewski M., Feuerlein S., Juchems M., and Hoffmann M. H., Coronary plaque imaging with 256-slice multidetector computed tomography: interobserver variability of volumetric lesion parameters with semiautomatic plaque analysis software, *Int J Cardiovasc Imaging*, vol. 26, pp. 711-20, Aug 2010.
- [17] Das M., Braunschweig T., Muhlenbruch G., Mahnken A. H., Krings T., Langer S., Koepfel T., Jacobs M., Gunther R. W., and Mommertz G., Carotid plaque analysis: comparison of dual-source computed tomography (CT) findings and histopathological correlation, *Eur J Vasc Endovasc Surg*, vol. 38, pp. 14-9, Jul 2009.